

Author: Morena Tartari

Affiliation: Universiteit Antwerpen (University of Antwerp), Belgium

Title: Single-Mums, Intersections, and the ‘work’ of legitimation and de-legitimation by institutions: early findings from a study in four EU countries

Abstract submitted to and accepted by the Centre for Research on Families & Relationships International Conference “Intersectionality, Families and Relationships”, 22-24 June 2020, Edinburgh (UK)

Adopting the sociological approach of Institutional Ethnography (IE) as a method, the Study on TRansition and Exclusion in Society of Single-Mums (STRESS-Mums) collects data in three EU countries (Belgium, Italy and Spain) and in the UK, with discursive interviews to lone mothers, professionals and gender issues activists, participant observations, and photo-voice.

The research concerns lone mothers’ everyday strategies and social practices to claim inclusion and to negotiate (or not negotiate) the dominant definition of family and parenthood proposed by institutions and professionals, and the less legitimated and multiple situated definitions of lone parents and their families. Analyzing the transition from double parenthood to lone motherhood, and, in particular, the period of judicial evaluation for child custody and judicial decisions for children/family allowances and divorce/separation, the study explores the lone mothers’ manifest and hidden ‘work’ of legitimation and of possible de-legitimation by institutions.

This paper discusses the early findings of this study focusing on how intersectionality may affect this ‘work’ of legitimation and de-legitimation, and how it leads to inequalities and to conditions of partial citizenship.

Furthermore, the paper highlights how Institutional Ethnography is a valuable approach and method for studying intersectionality and its effects in the single mums' everyday life.

This research project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no 843976.

Keywords:

Lone mothers, single mothers, gender citizenship, active citizenship, advocacy, everyday life sociology, Institutional Ethnography

Acknowledgements

The research project "Study on TRansition and Exclusion in Society of Single-Mums (STRESS-Mums)" has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no 843976.